

ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE, SELF-EFFICACY, AND WORK TASKS MOTIVATION: A PATH MODEL ON PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF MOTHER TONGUE BASED-MULTILINGUAL TEACHERS

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Organizational Climate, Self-Efficacy, and Work Tasks Motivation: A Path Model on Pedagogical Competence of Mother Tongue Based-Multilingual Teachers

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine best fit model of pedagogical competence of mother tongue based-multilingual (MTB-MLE) teachers as estimated by organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation among public elementary schools in Region XI, Philippines. It was conducted from August to December 2022. The study used quantitative, non-experimental research design using correlational technique and path analysis. The 400 teachers among public elementary schools were determined using the stratified sampling procedure. Mean, Pearson r, and path analysis were used as statistical tools. Moreover, adapted survey questionnaires were used. The result shows that the level organizational climate of MTB-MLE teachers was high while the levels of self-efficacy, work tasks motivation and pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers were very high. Further, when each exogenous variable is correlated to pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers, results showed that organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation were significantly correlated with the pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers. Model 3 came out as the best-fit path model that predicts the pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers. The model showed that self-efficacy and work tasks motivation have direct effect on pedagogical competence while organizational climate has indirect effect on pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers. This implies that schools may enhance their professional development programs by focusing on teachers' ability in MTB-MLE instruction.

Keywords: *organizational climate, self-efficacy, work tasks motivation pedagogical competence, path analysis, mother tongue based-multilingual teachers*

Introduction

Language-in-education has gained currency as a concern and a topic in the context of the Philippines as the country has shifted from the use of English to the utilization of Mother Tongues (MTs) as the language of instruction (Alieto, 2018). However, issues on the quality and competence of teachers in teaching mother tongue has emerged. It was contended that teachers' inappropriate instruction especially in terms of unsuitable language choice result in detrimental effects and dire consequences for mother tongue learners (Perez & Alieto, 2018). Moreover, problems on the literacy skills imparted to the learners by teachers fail to achieve the purpose for which it was intended and become irrelevant to the young learners. Also, issues on teachers' presentation skills of mother tongue has been explored to address this gap (Chebet, 2020). In addition, teachers are constrained in raising the quality of mother tongue competence as they face daily lack of adequate teachers' guide and students' textbooks (Parba, 2018).

Improving the pedagogical competence of teachers in language teaching is important. The development of pedagogical competence in improving the quality of teaching in languages, the use of innovative methods in the teaching process, and pedagogical professional training are contributory to the success of language learning (Shoimov, 2020). Further, pedagogical competence among mother tongue teachers is very crucial in implementing the mother tongue-based instruction. MTB teachers should acquire pedagogical competence in MTB instruction which requires them to have set of attitudes, skills and knowledge that are very important to effectively affect the learning of the learners (Mata, 2014). In the same vein, mother tongue teachers need to have motivation in implementing MTB instruction. Mother tongue teachers should be emotionally prepared which means they have to have motivation in order for them to effectively teach their learners with the use of mother tongue as the medium of instruction (Lartec, Belisario, Bendanillo, Binas-o, Novefirst, & Caammagay, 2014).

Considering the importance of pedagogical competence among mother tongue teachers, the researcher made some readings and analysis on the theory and few literature studies which revealed the factors which influence the pedagogical competence of teachers. The study was anchored on Competence Motivation Theory of White (1959). Competence Motivation Theory is a conceptual framework designed to explain individuals' motivation to participate, persist, and work hard in any particular achievement context. The central thesis of the theory is that individuals are attracted to participation in activities at which they feel competent or capable. The theory can be used by researchers and practitioners in adults can be encouraged to participate and to exert effort in these achievement contexts. This theory was used in this study with the existing propositions cited by various authors which established the relationship between the independent variables which are organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation and the dependent variable which is the pedagogical competence. Researches revealed that the climate of the school and motivation affects the pedagogical competence or performance of teachers. Work motivation and school climate have positive and significant influence upon teachers' teaching performance (Hakim, Sa'ud, Komariah & Sunaengsih, 2017; Selamat, Samsu & Kamalu, 2013). Further, teachers with higher level of motivation tend to have greater competence in teaching (Davidson, 2005; Mustafa & Othman, 2010; Nadeem, Rana, Lone, Maqbool, Naz & Ali, 2011). In addition, various researchers (Akay & Boz, 2011; Alkan & Erdem, 2012; Cherian & Jacob, 2013; Ogun & Topkaya, 2008; Sahin, 2010) mentioned that self-efficacy was associated with the pedagogical competence of teachers.

In addition, various literature and related studies are herein presented that lead to the understanding of the variables under consideration re organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation, and pedagogical competence.

On the concept of organizational climate, it is revealed that schools are the prime element in our education system. For personnel working in a school, adapting to schools' purpose, accepting the values, beliefs, and norms and behaving appropriately are within scope of organizational climate. There are many factors that affect organizational climate. But prime factor in organizational climate is people and interaction between groups. Interaction of school with its environment, the balance between the purpose of the school and individual's purpose the degree of the success of the realization of school's purpose, manager at school and other professional people's personal traits, are the primary effects on the organizational climate (Aydin, 2013; Bursahoglu, 2013; Ceyda & Sevinc, 2012; Topcu, 2008).

Moreover, one of the key conditions to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of the healthy climate school is organization climate. School researches point out that effective schools have positive organizational climate. If there is no positive organization climate, it is not possible to improve the school. Also, if there is open communications and sincere relations at school, then we can say that there is positive organizational climate at school. Positive climate is an important concept that will facilitate the success and welfare level we desire to see in schools. There are important responsibilities for school members in building an environment where they want to be a part of, and where mutual sincerity, trust and respect exist (Ceyda & Sevinc, 2012; Ozden, 2014; Taymaz, 2013).

The first indicator of organizational climate is institutional vulnerability. It is the extent to which the school is susceptible to a few vocal parents and citizen groups. High vulnerability suggests that both teachers and principals are unprotected and put on the defensive (Hoy et al., 2002). Relatively, we define institutional vulnerability as 'the combination of the weaknesses embedded in institutions (purpose or non-purpose built for disaster management) that reduce the capacity to resist/withstand/cope or recover from the impact of a hazardous event (Papathoma-Kohle & Thaler, 2018).

The second indicator is collegial leadership. This refers to principal behavior directed toward meeting both social needs of the faculty and achieving the goals of the school. The principal treats teachers as colleagues, is open, egalitarian, and friendly, but at the same time sets clear teacher expectations and standards of performance (Hoy et al., 2002). Likewise, collegial leadership is a type of collaborative leadership defined by behaviors, communication, and paradigms that may deepen and sustain collaborative processes and forces (Mooney, 2012; Soe & Than, 2020).

The third indicator is professional teacher behaviour. It is marked by respect for colleague competence, commitment to students, autonomous judgment, and mutual cooperation and support of colleagues (Bandura, 1997; Goddard & Goddard, 2001; Goddard, Hoy, & Woolfolk Hoy, 2004). In terms of autonomy, as a professional attitude, consists of the practitioner's desire to be free to make decisions about his work. These decisions, he feels, should be made without the threat of external pressures. Such pressures at the organizational level, represent the antithesis of professional autonomy (Snizek, 2013).

The last indicator is achievement press. It describes a school that sets high but achievable academic standards and goals. Students persist, strive to achieve, and are respected by both students and teachers for their academic success. Parents, teachers, and the principal all exert pressure for high standards and school improvement. (Hoy et al., 2002).

In terms of self-efficacy, it is presented that collective self-efficacy refers to the beliefs about the ability of teachers to execute courses of action required to produce given attainments. In fact, a school which is characterized by high collective teacher efficacy set challenging goals and are persistent in their effort to meet these goals (Bandura, 2016; Goddard, 2018; Goddard & Goddard, 2009; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2010).

Teacher self-efficacy is grounded in the theoretical framework of social cognitive theory emphasizing the evolvment and exercise of human agency that people can exercise some influence over what they do. Researchers maintained that in this conception, people are self-organizing, proactive, self-regulating, and self-reflecting. From this perspective, self-efficacy affects one's goals and behaviors and is influenced by one's actions and conditions in the environment. Efficacy beliefs determine how environmental opportunities and impediments are perceived and affect choice of activities, how much effort is expended on an activity, and how long people will persevere when confronting obstacles. Moreover, based on social cognitive theory teacher self-efficacy may be conceptualized as individual teachers' beliefs in their own ability to plan, organize, and carry out activities that are required to attain given educational goals. (Bandura, 2016; Pajares, 2009; Schunk & Meece, 2010).

A school cultural climate with high collective teacher efficacy promotes students' achievements which again enhance individual teachers' sense of self-efficacy. Therefore, it is expected that individual teacher self-efficacy and collective teacher efficacy are positively related. However, it is not obvious that being part of a strong team always increases self-efficacy for all team members. Based on social comparison theory one may expect that a teacher who perceive his or her teaching ability to be lower than the ability of other teachers at school may lose confidence regarding his or her own teaching ability. Hence, we conceptualize individual teacher self-efficacy and collective teacher efficacy can be conceptualized as different but correlated constructs (Marsh & Craven, 2011; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2018).

Moreover, Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2010) recently developed a multidimensional 24-item Norwegian Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale

(NTSES) measuring six dimensions by four items each. The dimensions were self-efficacy for instruction, adapting education to individual students' needs, motivating students, keeping discipline, cooperating with colleagues and parents, and coping with changes and challenges.

The first domain of teacher self-efficacy is instruction. This dimension refers to the skills in explaining central themes in subjects so that even the low achieving students understand; providing good guidance and instruction to all students regardless of their level of ability; answering students' questions so that they understand difficult problems; and explaining subject matter so that most students understand the basic principles. An important task for all teachers is to explain subject matter so that students understand the basic principles. This dimension focuses on the teacher's expectation of being able to instruct students, explain subject matter, and answer questions to improve students' understanding (Avanzi, Balducci, Khezerlou, Miglioretti & Vecchio, 2013; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2010).

The second domain is adapting instruction to individual needs. This dimension refers to the skill in organizing schoolwork to adapt instruction and assignments to individual needs; providing realistic challenge for all students even in mixed ability classes; and adapting instruction to the needs of low-ability students while also attending to the needs of other students in class. Likewise, it involves organizing classroom work so that both low- and high-ability students work with tasks that are adapted to their abilities. Moreover, it emphasizes the teachers' beliefs in their ability to adapt education to the needs and abilities of individual students, bearing student diversity in mind (Avanzi et al., 2013, Khezerlou, 2013; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2010).

The third domain is motivating students. This dimension refers to the skill in getting all students in class to work hard with their schoolwork; waking the desire to learn even among the lowest-achieving students; getting students to do their best even when working with difficult problems and motivating students who show low interest in schoolwork. Moreover, it refers to teachers' beliefs in their ability to involve students in teaching/learning activities (Avanzi et al., 2013, Khezerlou, 2013; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2010).

The fourth domain is maintaining discipline. This dimension refers to the skill in maintaining discipline in any school class or group of students; controlling even the most aggressive students; getting students with behavioral problems to follow classroom rules; and getting all students to behave politely and respect the teachers. Keeping discipline is a sense of ability to deal with students misbehaviors (Avanzi et al., 2013, Khezerlou, 2013; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2010).

The fifth domain is cooperating with colleagues and parents. This refers to the skill in terms of cooperating well with most parents; finding adequate solutions to conflicts of interest with other teachers; collaborating constructively with parents of students with behavioral problems; and cooperating effectively and constructively with other teachers, for example, in teaching teams. Likewise, it is a sense of desire to cooperate with others to solve problems (Avanzi et al., 2013, Khezerlou, 2013; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2010).

Lastly, the domain coping with change refers to the skill in terms of successfully using any instructional method that the school decides to use; managing instruction regardless of how it is organized (group composition, mixed age groups, etc.); managing instruction even if the curriculum is changed and teaching well even if you are told to use instructional methods that would not be your choose. It is a sense of desire to adapt oneself to methodological and situational changes (Avanzi et al., 2013, Khezerlou, 2013; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2010).

In the context of work tasks motivation, various researches have focused on the notion of motivation and teaching (Deci & Ryan, 2014; Ryan & Brown, 2015; Ryan & Deci, 2009; Soenens, Sierens, Vansteenkiste, Goossens & Dochy, 2012; Ten Cate, Kusrkar & Williams, 2011). A wide-ranging review of literature establish three foremost themes on motivation such as factors of the motivation of teachers, mechanisms to modify instructional practices, and the effect of motivationally-based pedagogical activities on student achievements (Black & Deci, 2010; Filak & Sheldon, 2013; Niemiec, Lynch, Vansteenkiste, Bernstein, Deci & Ryan, 2016; Perlman, 2011; 2012; Perlman & Piletic, 2012; Tessier, Sarrazin & Ntoumanis, 2010; Williams, Saizow, Ross & Deci, 2017).

Furthermore, teacher motivation can be defined as the interest, enthusiasm, or desire in teachers to be focused on endeavoring efforts to offer learners some assistance with learning. At the point when teachers are motivated to teach effectively, a school can accomplish its objective of giving quality learning and training to the pupils. Besides, motivation seems to be an effective instrument that teachers need in their job. Teachers can perform competently and effectively if they have high level of motivation. Also, motivation is of great importance for teachers since it affects their job satisfaction and performance. The teachers are more committed and involved in their work if they are highly satisfied and motivated. In addition, teachers' job motivation can have a helpful effect on pupils' achievement. Hence, teachers must be interested enough to do their jobs excellently. Otherwise, they cannot teach effectively (Bieg, Backes & Mittag, 2011; Kim & Cho, 2014; Recepoglu, 2013).

Moreover, there is multidimensional nature of the work tasks motivation of teachers which can be measured in terms of identified, introjected, and external regulations and amotivation. A Work Tasks Motivation Scale for Teachers was created that measures motivation of teachers in a multidimensional way while bearing in mind the work tasks domain. It was seen to be an effective measuring tool for investigating teachers' motivational practices and emotional functioning at work. Most researches adapt this in order to better understand why teachers are in quandary about their absence of work motivation (Chemolli & Gagne, 2014; Fernet et al., 2008; Guay, Chanal, Ratelle, Marsh, Larose & Boivin, 2010).

The first domain is intrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation alludes to perform a task for its innate satisfaction as opposed to for some

distinguishable result. At the point when intrinsically motivated, individuals take part in tasks that interest them, and they do as such openly, with a full feeling of volition and without the need of material rewards or requirements. Individuals who are inherently motivated feel that they are doing an action since they have done as such voluntarily and since the activity characterizes a challenge to their prevailing competencies and necessitate them to utilize their creative abilities. This type of motivation is regarded as highly self-determined because of the reason for performing the activity is associated exclusively to the person's positive outlooks while doing the task (Deci & Ryan, 2010; Deci, Vallerand, Pelletier & Ryan, 2011; Jarvela & Jarvenoja, 2011; Noels, Clement & Pelletier, 2009).

In the same vein, intrinsically motivated individuals are said to experience satisfaction and pleasure if they actively perform a certain task or work. Conversely, individuals who have low self-determination are not actively involved in their job and are detached in learning tasks because they perceive activities as not enjoyable (Fernet et al., 2008; Jarvela & Jarvenoja, 2011; Niemiec et al., 2016). In school climate, intrinsically motivated teachers are seen to provide a pedagogical setting that positively influenced pupils' motivation. As such, some studies confirmed the concept that being more intrinsically motivated is associated with more constructive outcomes in the school climate (Bachore, 2014; Bieg et al., 2011; Ofoegbu, 2014; Perlman & Piletic, 2012).

The second domain is identified regulation. Identified regulation is characterized as conduct that people perform on the grounds that it is consistent with their own particular qualities and objectives. Rather than succumbing to outside or inward pressures, people experience decision while doing the task, in spite of the fact that the task is not inherently motivating (Gillison, Osborn, Standage & Skevington, 2009; Ryan & Deci, 2009; Teixeira, Carraca, Markland, Silva & Ryan, 2012).

Besides, it alludes to doing an activity since one identifies with its worth or meaning and acknowledges it as one's own, such this form of internalization is volitional. Identification contrasts from intrinsic motivation in that the activity is not done out of inherent fulfillment, but rather for the instrumental worth it speaks to. In conjunction, this is a form of extrinsic motivation which depends on the self-supported value of a certain task. Teachers who have identified motivation are thought to be more self-ruling than the teachers with external motivation yet they are not as completely self-sufficient as those with intrinsically motivated teachers (Kim & Cho, 2014; Ryan, Lynch, Vansteenkiste & Deci, 2011).

The third domain is introjected motivation. Introjected regulation refers to the mode whereby an outer interest turns into an inside representation. People put weight on themselves through inner intimidation, (for example, anxiety, guilt, or shame) to ensure that a specific conduct is performed. Similarly, introjected regulation refers to the regulation of conduct out of inside compelling forces, for example, ego-involvement. It said that this type of internalization is usually experienced as controlling (Fernet et al., 2008; Nicholls, 2014; Ryan, 2012; Verstuyf, Patrick, Vansteenkiste & Teixeira, 2012).

In addition, introjected regulation of behavior refers to embracing regulations to behavior but not completely accepting the regulations as your own. This behavior usually characterizes regulation by contingent self-esteem, alluding to ego involvement as a typical form of introjections. This is the type of behavior where individuals feel motivated to exhibit aptitude to uphold self-esteem. Despite the fact that this is internally determined, introjected behavior has an outward observed locus of connectedness. From the time when the connectedness of the behavior is observed as external, the behavior is reflected non-self-determined (Deci & Ryan, 2010; Murcia, Roman, Galindo, Alonso & Gonzalez-Cutre, 2008; Pelletier, Tuson, Green-Demers, Noels & Beaton, 2008; Soenens et al., 2012).

The fourth domain is external regulation. It happens when behaviors are directed to get a prize or to stay away from any constraints. External motivation signifies that one's conduct is controlled by outer forces, for example, external pressures or financial rewards. It speaks to the most reduced level of self-directed motivation (Assor, Vansteenkiste & Kaplan, 2009; Fernet et al., 2008; Kim & Cho, 2014; Ryan, Deci, Grolnick & La Guardia, 2016). In the same manner, it alludes to doing an action with a specific end goal to get compensation or stay away from reprimands. This type of behavior is said to be non-internalized. Additionally, as external regulation encompasses a sense of coercion and pressure, it characterizes examples of a controlled motivation (Demir, 2011; Ofoegbu, 2014).

Furthermore, this motivation which is related to extrinsic motivation which results from the completion of externally directed rewards, including wages, material assets, reputation, and positive appraisals from other people. Specifically, teachers' extrinsic motivation comprised externally directed rewards like compensation, weekly duty and additional teaching allowances, advance disbursements and leave of absence (Mary, 2010; Sansone & Harackiewicz, 2010).

The last domain is amotivation. Amotivated individuals are said to be neither extrinsically nor intrinsically motivated. Amotivation relates to the low level of self-determination. People are amotivated when they have no aim of participating in a specific conduct and don't generally know why they are doing it. Likewise, amotivation is seen as an absence of motivation or yearning as seen in individuals who don't participate in behavior regardless of what number of external stimuli is given (Barkoukisa, Tsorbatzoudis, Grouiosa & Sideridi, 2008; Perlman, 2011; Perlman, 2013).

Lastly, in terms of pedagogical competence, research studies in the Philippines and other countries provide evidence that policy makers should be convinced of the possible benefits of mother tongue instruction for pupils who belong in the language minority. It has been highlighted that mother tongue instruction can enhance academic skills; stimulate classroom interaction and participation; augment educational access and develop critical thinking skills (Benson, 2014; Brock-Utne, 2016; Cummins, 2010; Dutcher, 2013; Smits, Huisman & Kruijff, 2008; Thomas & Collier, 2010). Research has also indicated the impact of multilingual education on cultural identity and egotism and improves parental involvement and develops achievement (Benson, 2015; Cummins, 2010; Dutcher, 2013; D

‘Emilio, 2015; Hovens, 2012; Walter & Dekker, 2011; Wright & Taylor, 2015).

Further, mother tongue-based instruction includes the instruction using the learners’ first language or mother tongue. The instruction is usually with a prearranged gradual transition to a second language at a definite time in elementary school. This generally happens solely in the dialect most well-known to the learner. Learners have the chance to learn core ideas fundamentally in a well-known dialect, and later, they take in the vocabulary for those ideas in another language (Naom & Sarah, 2014; Pflapson, 2011; Sure & Webb, 2010).

In conjunction, numerous studies have uncovered that teaching utilizing the mother tongue as a part of the early years of schooling upgrades learners’ capacity to learn better compared with the utilization of a second language. It has additionally been accounted for that if learners are taught in language which are different in relation to their home dialect or native language, they drop out from school, have low academic achievement, and repeat classes because of a high failure rate. This situation still exists in Nepal. Research on L2 acquisition demonstrates that when a learner masters the mother tongue then taking in another language turns out to be less problematic in the habits for discourse, listening, reading, and writing. Research that has been conducted on language education has also revealed that learners are quicker to learn, to read, and to gain other academic aptitudes when taught in the dialect that they talk at home instead of the languages that are new to them (Ndamba, 2008; Rai, Rai, Phyak & Rai, 2011; Malone, 2017).

Similarly, mother-tongue based instruction has become gradually essential educational principle to make the language of the learners, culture and climate as the basis of learning and that there are some evidences which showed some advantages of educating the learners in their mother tongue especially on their reading skills. Some studies revealed that mother tongue based instruction helps develop the ability of pupils to learn better. This further implies that mother-tongue education necessitates teachers who are well-versed with the culture and language of the learners, hence, who have proficient macro-skills of the learners’ first language (Benson et al., 2010; Dea, Basha & Abera, 2014; Rai et al., 2011).

Moreover, researchers forward different advantages of doing classes through mother tongue. At the point when content of the curriculum is presented in a language that is not familiar, a huge amount of time must be spent first teaching learners to comprehend, talk, read, and compose second language, something that is extremely challenging and squanders profitable years in the early grades that could be spent figuring out how to peruse and learning academic ideas in mother tongue. Besides, learners, who can’t comprehend the language utilized in the classroom, can’t show what they know, make inquiries, and take an interest. Conversely, giving learners a chance to learn in a language they comprehend—beginning on the first day of school—presents critical focal points for the training framework, teachers, parents and learners (Ball, 2010; Bender & Dutcher, 2015; Smits et al., 2008).

Likewise, numerous studies have also uncovered that utilizing the first language as a part of the early grades upgrades the learners’ capacity to learn better. It has additionally been accounted for that if kids are taught in dialects which are not quite the same as their home dialect or primary language, they drop out from school, have low scholastic performance, and rehash classes because of high rate of failures. This implies mother tongue instruction requires educators who share the culture and dialect of the learners (Benson et al., 2010; Rai et al., 2011).

Subsequently, the use of mother tongue instruction is evident in most countries. In Kenya, it was evident that teachers’ attitude towards the teaching and use of mother tongue as a language of instruction. However, it shows that mother tongue is least preferred for instruction than Kiswahili and English. It was observed that teachers desire to see learners utilizing English than their first language during instruction (Khejeri, 2014; Puhakka, 2015; Sibomana, 2016).

In the same manner, teachers implement the MTB instruction in a multilingual climate with the use of translation of the target language to learners’ first language. They also use multilingual instruction and they are seen to be using lingua-franca, creating learning materials written in the learners’ first language, doing remedial instruction and using literary texts transcribed in the learners’ first language. Through the use of this varied activities employed by MTB teachers, they become more effective in delivering MTB lessons which in turn assist pupils’ acquisition of information and learning. These inventive strategies cause the pupils to achieve high level of learning and develop their written and oral skills. Nonetheless, there are problems being experienced by the mother tongue teachers such as the shortage of books written in the mother tongue and lack of vocabulary and training. This dilemma needs to be addressed in order for teachers’ not to struggle in delivering MTB lessons and will not hinder the effective learning of MTB pupils (Lartec et al., 2014; Milambiling, 2011; Rai et al., 2011).

In consonance, pedagogical competences are part of teachers’ professional competence. Pedagogical competence refers to the capability of teachers to utilize organized concrete and intangible resources to attain pedagogical effectiveness and efficacy. Further, pedagogical competences characterize the capacity and motivation often applies to the knowledge, skills and attitudes that support the learning of the pupils in the most effective way. Also, competence commonly refers to ability; however, the term has more multifaceted meaning since it comprises a set of skills, knowledge, values and attitudes. Apparently, the job of mother tongue teachers is crucial since they have to acquire pedagogical competence in the mother tongue instruction. Pedagogical competence in MTB instruction encompasses the teachers’ set of attitudes, skills and knowledge that are very important to effectively affect pupils’ learning (Madhavaram & Laverie, 2010; Mata, 2014; Ryegard, 2010).

In the same vein, expounding a system of professional standards for mother-tongue teachers adds to producing an influential and

accessible teaching body. Evidently, the improvement of competency qualifications for mother-tongue teachers may considerably add to quality assurance. They offer an arduous approach in which to recognize, postulate and assess the least possible skills that mother tongue teachers ought to show in order to afford high quality language learning. Competent and motivated teachers are desired for the implementation of mother-tongue teaching. These teachers must have both established advanced language competences and concrete methodological-didactic competencies (Ingram, 2017; Liddicoat, Tognini, Fischmann, Harbon, Kohler & McLaughlin, 2015; Mata, 2014; Oser & Renold, 2016).

Relatively, there was no consensus about the base structure of the professional standards of mother tongue teachers. However, there has been a lot of effort which tries to define what the MTB teachers should possess. In fact, there were holistic categories of professional standards being established for the purpose of uniting varied perspectives about the professional competencies of MTB teachers. A model was shaped which integrates the basic strategies, skills, knowledge, and values that the MTB teachers should possess. This model presents the pedagogical competencies which are structured into six domains (Mata, 2014).

The first domain is competence to assure the functionality of the educational process. It alludes to teachers' capacity to utilize classroom and additional classroom learning encounters and exercises to work on utilizing the primary dialect and culture in real-world circumstances. This means that it is important for teachers to integrate culture in language activities and tasks in order to provide a climate and a real-life purpose for language (Allen, 2014; Clementi & Terrill, 2013; Mata, 2014). In this area, teachers have the responsibility to develop the moral, creativity, physical, intellectual and technological learning of the pupils into the mother tongue instruction, and encourage the compliance of the didactic standards into mother tongue instruction (De Jong & Harper, 2015; Mata, 2014; Ranaweera, 2010; Rassekh & Vaideanu, 2017).

Further, it is important for teachers to align mother tongue curriculum contents with the intellectual and physical needs and abilities of learners. Moreover, teachers should facilitate the compliance of principles of education into mother tongue instruction such as utilizing authentic classroom learning activities and experiences by using the learners' first language and culture in real-world climates (Mata, 2014; Ranaweera, 2010; Rassekh & Vaideanu, 2017).

The second domain is ability to design curriculum. This alludes to how the curriculum established at the national level is being applied into mother tongue instruction and choosing appropriate curricular resources for mother tongue instruction. Concerned mother tongue teachers should back up culturally climatealized curriculum in the MTB instruction with suitable and appropriate curriculum materials which are written in mother tongue that is relevant to pupils (Mackenzie, 2010; Mackenzie & Walker, 2015; Mata, 2014). Moreover, this domain is done by incorporating the explicit knowledge, abilities, skills, values, attitudes, and behavior for mother tongue acquisition (Ingram, 2017; Mata, 2014; Svobodova & Gejgusova, 2016).

The third domain is capacity to establish the finalities of education. It refers to choosing competences for the mother tongue and making the substantial objectives MTB language and literature lessons (Kelly, Grenfell, Allan, Kriza & McEvoy, 2014; Mata, 2014; Tulasiewicz & Adams, 2015).

In particular, it includes teachers' competence in selecting general and specific competences from the lesson guides, formulating concrete objectives for a language lesson in one's mother tongue, and formulating concrete objectives for a literature lesson in one's mother tongue. The aspects of such capacity as teachers adeptly consider important competencies for their lesson. This further implies that mother tongue teachers should have enough capacity to create significant outcomes for MTB lessons (Kelly et al., 2014; Mata, 2014; Tulasiewicz & Adams, 2015).

The fourth domain is competence in the use of specific teaching strategies. It involves utilizing particular teaching methods and learning of the mother tongue and integrating explicit didactic tools to facilitate pupils to use the mother tongue in authentic situations. Likewise, it includes the capacity of teacher to combine class teaching, pair drills and individualized learning in mother-tongue instruction (Haines, 2015; Harmer, 2011; Liddicoat et al., 2015; Nolasco & Arthur, 2008; Mata, 2014; Ritchhart, 2012).

Pursuing the above concept, mother tongue teachers should employ teaching tools that will allow and encourage the pupils to use their mother tongue to access the curriculum. Such as they may complete lesson tasks and assessments in their mother tongue and they are stimulated to share their knowledge and growth with their parents and other people in the community using their mother tongue. Also, in mother tongue instruction teachers should know how to employ paired work with individual learning since it has advantage to teaching. It is said that it gives pupils more time for conversation, cooperation and autonomy. It also allows for individual differences in learning style (Haines, 2015; Harmer, 2011; Mata, 2014; Nolasco & Arthur, 2008; Ritchhart, 2012).

The fifth domain is ability to design the teaching activity. It includes explaining the yearly and semestral design for the MTB language and literature subject and devising plans for diverse types of mother tongue lessons. It also includes the skill to fashion opportunities to utilize the mother tongue outside the school. This implies that mother tongue teachers should have the ability to design effective instructional plans that will assist the language acquisition and learning of MTB learners. Likewise, mother tongue teachers need to plan task-based activities that allow learners to use their mother tongue in climatealized situations (Mata, 2014; North, 2009; Wang, 2011).

Also, in mother tongue instruction, it is important to have the involvement of the local culture of MTB learners in the classroom by

selecting and developing suitable language teaching activities within the background of the local culture of the learners. For mother tongue pupils to raise the value of their language, they need to be completely immersed with the language. This can be realized with the learning materials and activities prepared and designed by the teachers according to the needs and interests of the learners. Teaching in mother tongue will be effective when sufficient and appropriate learning activities and materials are used (McKay, 2013; Sunday & Joshua, 2010).

Further, teachers should have the skills in designing activities that develop the awareness of the learners of their individual culture, in providing stimulating, interesting and challenging tasks related to mother tongue language-based learning employing innovative activities and in instigating school-wide activities associated to mother tongue language-based learning. Additionally, it is worth noting that parents and the communities should be encouraged by teachers to be part in designing activities that would support the mother tongue-based learning implementation (Naom & Sarah, 2014; Navarro, Abao, Bacus, Alda & Espera, 2016).

The last domain is competence to use the specific assessment strategies. It encompasses the teachers' ability to create preliminary, formative, and summative assessment tools to measure the level of mother tongue learning by pupils and who utilize particular assessment methods of knowledge and skills for pupils' mother tongue acquisition. It also refers to the capacity of teachers to utilize particular assessment methods of values, behaviors and attitudes for pupils' mother tongue learning (Bachore, 2014; Mata, 2014; Oser & Renold, 2016; Starc, 2014).

Likewise, mother tongue teachers considered that the most imperative pedagogical factor was using specific methods of knowledge assessment to measure the abilities and skills of pupils in first language acquisition. Teachers need to assess the learners' perception and attitudes towards mother tongue instruction in order to meet the classroom demands (Bachore, 2014; Mata, 2014; Oser & Renold, 2016; Starc, 2014).

In conjunction, several related studies revealed the relationship of the variables such as the organizational climate, self-efficacy, work tasks motivation and pedagogical competence. Researches revealed that the climate of the school and motivation affects the pedagogical competence or performance of teachers. In any organization, the organizational climate or climate and work motivation contributes to the performance or competence of its employees. Work motivation and school climate have positive and significant influence upon teachers' teaching performance. Hence, these are important factors in increasing teaching competence (Hakim, Sa'ud, Komariah & Sunaengsih, 2017).

Similarly, a study specifically exposed the significant relationship between the climate of the workplace and pedagogical competence or performance of teachers. The workplace climate was found to be a significant factor that could affect teachers' job performance (Selamat, Samsu & Kamalu, 2013).

In addition, self-efficacy was seen to be a factor influencing the performance of individuals at workplace and the mechanism by which self-efficacy of an individual determines his/her work-related performance. In particular, self-efficacy was associated with the pedagogical competence of teachers. There is a positive relationship between self-efficacy scores and professional competency scores of teachers (Akay & Boz, 2011; Alkan & Erdem, 2012; Cherian & Jacob, 2013; Ogus & Topkaya, 2008; Sahin, 2010).

Additionally, there have been some researches about the relationship between teacher motivation and their performance or competence in teaching. It was concluded that there is a significant relationship between the motivation factors and the teachers' competence in teaching (Nadeem et. al, 2011).

Further, motivation is one factor that was seen to influence the pedagogical competence of teachers. Teachers with higher level of motivation tend to have greater competence in teaching. Moreover, if teachers experienced a motivating work environment, they tend to have increased teaching competence and performance. This signifies that building the teachers' level of motivation will enhance the instruction framework (Davidson, 2005; Mustafa & Othman, 2010; Nadeem, Rana, Lone, Maqbool, Naz & Ali, 2011).

In fact, in the study conducted by Silverio (2016), it was pointed out that motivation of mother tongue teachers play as a significant aspect in augmenting their pedagogical competence particularly on their competence to assure the quality and functionality of the MTB curriculum and the competence to utilize important MTB teaching strategies and assessment. Thus, MTB Filipino teachers need a particular motivation in such a way that the greater the level of motivation they have, the higher will be their job performance or competence specifically with their ability to plan MTB pedagogy and with their capacity to formulating authentic outcomes for language learning.

Most studies examined teachers' perceptions about the effects of motivation on their work performance and competence. It found out that there is a positive relation between motivation and teachers' working performance, which means that if teachers have higher level of motivation, they will also have greater performance or competence in teaching. Moreover, if teachers experienced a motivating work environment, they tend to have increased teaching competence and performance. The primary advantages of motivation are that the school can utilize the teachers' labor in a proper path, for this the teachers are willing to work themselves. It brings teachers' fulfillment and the objectives can be accomplished on time in school. Along these lines, the effectiveness and ability boosts and its expense get to be decreased (Mustafa & Othman, 2010; Robbins, Judge & Sanghi, 2005).

Moreover, a study investigated that from the teachers' perspectives in schools, motivation and performance are not the same. Motivation

is an input to work, and job performance is an output from this motivation. For instance, satisfaction is another very vital thing in terms of motivation so teachers are when content with their work and teaching environment, then inevitably get motivated and show their greatest efforts headed for their competence and performance. In conjunction, motivation plays an important role in the organization because it increases the competence of employees and the goals can be achieved in an efficient way. The behavior of employees can be change through motivation in any organization. From situation to situation, the level of motivation differs with in an individual (Robbins et al., 2005).

In addition, teachers' motivation towards their job is important. Teacher motivation is directly associated to their attitudes towards their work. It is true that motivation is mainly concerned with goal-directed performance. The motivation of teachers for instance is the enthusiasm to employ high level of encouragement to reach teaching-learning goals, conditioned by the hard work and capacity to satisfy some specific needs. It obviously shows that motivation is the willingness of teachers to do excellent and quality teaching competently and this take place only where their needs are fulfilled (Ajzen, 1998; Aziz, 2012; Bishay, 1996; Cox, Preston & Cox, 1999).

In the same vein, various studies concentrated on teachers' job in giving great quality learning in grade schools through motivation where it proposed a few activities to build the teachers' level of motivation that will enhance the instruction framework. It was stipulated that the school organization influences teachers' competence and performance in a negative or positive way. When the school organization don't make an appropriate motivational climate so unquestionably teachers will feel stress as a result of awful communication between other teachers and their school heads and their teaching performance won't meet the set standards. It was found that the amotivating working and living conditions have adverse effect on the competence and performance of teachers. It is fundamental to consider the terms and climate of school with the end goal of achieving high motivation of teachers (Davidson, 2005; Kadzamira, 2006).

In consonance, motivation and performance are vital factors for the success and accomplishments of an organization such as the school organization. The external changes in the environment necessitates the organization to assume that alterations since it could motivate employees to be competitive enough. This means that the main requirement is the expert and capable employees. Furthermore, teachers tend to be not motivated due to social and economic conditions and this have also affected teacher competence. Hence, motivational factors influence the competence of teachers and teachers' efficiency (Latt, 2008; Nadeem et al., 2011).

The above-mentioned studies provide evidence about the great importance of motivation of teachers in the field of education. If teachers are not motivated and having low performance then they cannot give their best efforts. Hence, head teachers or principals need to recognize that which things motivate the teachers due which they could improve their performance (Inayatullah & Jehangir, 2013).

Furthermore, the foregoing presentation and discussion of various literatures have helped in bringing into focus the important variables of the study; organizational climate, self-efficacy, work tasks motivation and pedagogical competence. These served as support to the results and findings of the study.

In this context, Figure 1 shows shows the conceptual framework showing the variables of the study. The independent variables of the study are the organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation while the dependent variable is the pedagogical competence. The first exogenous is the organizational climate with the following indicators, namely; institutional vulnerability, collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour, and achievement press (Hoy et al., 2002). The first indicator is institutional vulnerability which refers to the extent to which the school is susceptible to a few vocal parents and citizen groups. The second indicator is collegial leadership which refers to principal behavior directed toward meeting both social needs of the faculty and achieving the goals of the school. The third indicator is professional teacher behavior which is marked by respect for colleague competence, commitment to students, autonomous judgment, and mutual cooperation and support of colleagues. The last indicator is achievement press which describes a school that sets high but achievable academic standards and goals.

The second exogenous variable is self-efficacy of teachers with the following indicators, namely; instruction, adapting instruction to individual needs, motivating students, maintaining discipline, cooperating with colleagues and parents, and coping with change (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2010). The first indicator of teacher self-efficacy is instruction which refers to the skills of being able to instruct students, explain subject matter, and answer questions to improve students' understanding. The second indicator is adapting instruction to individual needs which refers to the skill in organizing schoolwork to adapt instruction and assignments to individual needs; providing realistic challenge for all students even in mixed ability classes; and adapting instruction to the needs of low-ability students while also attending to the needs of other students in class. The third indicator is motivating students which refers to the skill in getting all students in class to work hard with their schoolwork; waking the desire to learn even among the lowest-achieving students; getting students to do their best even when working with difficult problems and motivating students who show low interest in schoolwork. The fourth indicator is maintaining discipline which refers to the skill in maintaining discipline in any school class or group of students; controlling even the most aggressive students; getting students with behavioral problems to follow classroom rules; and getting all students to behave politely and respect the teachers. The fifth indicator is cooperating with colleagues and parents which refer to the sense of desire to cooperate with others to solve problems. Lastly, the indicator is coping with change refers to the sense of desire to adapt oneself to methodological and situational changes.

The third exogenous variable is the work task motivation of teachers with the following indicators, namely; intrinsic motivation, identified regulation, introjected regulation, external regulation and amotivation (Fernet et al., 2008). The first indicator is intrinsic motivation which refers to being able to perform a task for its innate satisfaction as opposed to for some distinguishable result. The second indicator is identified regulation which is characterized as conduct that people perform on the grounds that it is consistent with their own particular qualities and objectives. The third indicator is introjected motivation which refers to the mode whereby an outer interest turns into an inside representation. The fourth indicator is external regulation which happens when behaviors are directed to get a prize or to stay away from any constraints. The last indicator is amotivation which relates to the low level of self-determination and also it is seen as an absence of motivation or yearning as seen in individuals who don't participate in behavior regardless of what number of external stimuli is given.

The endogenous variable of this study is the pedagogical competence of mother tongue teachers with the following indicators, namely; competence to assure the functionality of the educational process, ability to design curriculum, capacity to establish the finalities of education, competence in the use of specific teaching strategies, ability to design the teaching activity, and competence to use the specific assessment strategies (Mata, 2014). The first indicator is competence to assure the functionality of the educational process which refers to teachers' capacity to utilize classroom and additional classroom learning encounters and exercises to work on utilizing the primary dialect and culture in real-world circumstances. The second indicator is ability to design curriculum which refers to how the curriculum established at the national level is being applied into mother tongue instruction and choosing appropriate curricular resources for mother tongue instruction. The third indicator is capacity to establish the finalities of education which refers to choosing competences for the mother tongue and making the substantial objectives MTB language and literature lessons. The fourth indicator is competence in the use of specific teaching strategies which involves utilizing particular teaching methods and learning of the mother tongue and integrating explicit didactic tools to facilitate pupils to use the mother tongue in authentic situations. The fifth indicator is ability to design the teaching activity which includes the ability to design effective instructional plans that will assist the language acquisition and learning of MTB learners. The last indicator is competence to use the specific assessment strategies which refers to the capacity of teachers to utilize particular assessment methods of values, behaviors and attitudes for pupils' mother tongue learning.

In consideration with the foregoing assumptions, the researcher has not come across of a study that dealt on a structural equation model on pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers using three exogenous variables, namely; organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation in the local setting. It is in the above context that the researcher decided to conduct the study with the intention of determining which of the above-mentioned variables may affect pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. Although there are already existing literatures on the association between organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation with work competence such as of teachers' pedagogical competence, those studies dealt only with bivariate relationships and did not cover the four variables in a single study. Only few of these researchers were conducted in the educational settings especially on teachers. This study will deal with the three exogenous variables and one endogenous variable, making this study a contribution to new knowledge. Further, this study can raise concern to the intended beneficiaries of this study and possibly develop action plans to augment the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers among schools using the independent variables organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation, thus, the need to conduct this study.

Consequently, the main thrust of this study was to determine the best fit model of pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers as estimated by organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation among public elementary schools in Region XI, Philippines. Moreover, this study aimed to describe the level of organizational climate in terms of institutional vulnerability, collegial leadership, professional teacher behavior, and achievement press; to ascertain the level of self-efficacy of teachers in terms of instruction, adapting instruction to individual needs, motivating students, maintaining discipline, cooperating with colleagues and parents, and coping with change; to determine the level of work tasks motivation of teachers in terms of intrinsic motivation, identified regulation, introjected regulation, external regulation, and amotivation; to determine the level of pedagogical competence of teachers in terms of competence to assure the functionality of the educational process, ability to design curriculum, capacity to establish the finalities of education, competence in the use of specific teaching strategies, ability to design the teaching activity, and competence to use the specific assessment strategies; to determine the significance of the relationship between organizational climate and pedagogical competence of teachers, self-efficacy and pedagogical competence of teachers, and work tasks motivation and pedagogical competence of teachers; and lastly, to determine the best fit model on the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers among public elementary schools in Region XI.

In consonance with the above objectives, the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. It was hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between organizational climate and pedagogical competence of teachers, self-efficacy and pedagogical competence of teachers, and work tasks motivation and pedagogical competence of teachers. Also, it was hypothesized that there is no model best fits the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers among public elementary schools in Region XI.

Remarkably, improving the pedagogical competence of teachers in language teaching is of global importance. The development of pedagogical competence in improving the quality of teaching in languages, the use of innovative methods in the teaching process, and pedagogical professional training are contributory to the success of language learning (Shoimov, 2020). Further, pedagogical

competence among mother tongue teachers is very crucial in implementing the mother tongue-based instruction. MTB teachers should acquire pedagogical competence in MTB instruction which requires them to have set of attitudes, skills and knowledge that are very important to effectively affect the learning of the learners (Mata, 2014). In the same vein, mother tongue teachers need to have motivation in implementing MTB instruction. Mother tongue teachers should be emotionally prepared which means they have to have motivation in order for them to effectively teach their learners with the use of mother tongue as the medium of instruction (Lartec et al., 2014).

Exploring pedagogical competence among mother tongue teachers is of social value in the context of education. Pedagogical competence among mother tongue teachers very crucial in implementing the mother tongue-based instruction. MTB teachers should acquire pedagogical competence in MTB instruction which requires them to have set of attitudes, skills and knowledge that are very important to effectively affect the learning of the learners. In the same vein, mother tongue teachers need to have motivation in implementing MTB instruction. Mother tongue teachers should be emotionally prepared which means they have to have motivation in order for them to effectively teach their learners with the use of mother tongue as the medium of instruction.

The findings of this study may be beneficial to the Department of Education, school heads, teachers, pupils and even the future researchers. The result of the study may give information to the Department of Education officials regarding the school organizational climate, self-efficacy, work tasks motivation and pedagogical competence of mother tongue teachers which may serve as the basis for the formulation of plans and programs that may augment these factors especially in the implementation of mother tongue-based instruction. Also, they may provide more in-service trainings and seminars that may help enhance the competence of teachers in teaching the mother tongue to pupils. Moreover, the result of the study may be beneficial to the school heads since they may acquire ample knowledge and information about the attitudes and situations experienced by mother tongue teachers. Hence, this study may give an enough idea to school heads for crafting necessary initiatives to assist teachers in language learning on the mother tongue, classroom instruction and its implementation. They may also assess how school climate, self-efficacy and work tasks motivation affects their competence in teaching. Consequently, findings of this study may also help the mother tongue teachers in such a way that they may be aware of their attitudes and motivation towards the implementation of mother tongue instruction. The teachers may find ways and mechanisms to develop their pedagogical competence in teaching mother tongue especially on their specific methods of teaching and learning and in designing a teaching activities and assessment strategies that will help gauge the abilities of pupils in their mother tongue. In addition, the findings of this study may benefit the pupils since if teachers' self-efficacy, work tasks motivation and pedagogical competence towards mother tongue instruction will make breakthrough enrichment, pupils' language learning and reading comprehension may be realized and developed. Likewise, this study would serve as springboard of the future researcher for further studies about the related variables and related studies.

Methodology

Presented in this section are the discussions on the research respondents, materials and instrument, and design and procedure.

The respondents of the study were the 400 MTB-MLE teachers among public elementary schools in Region XI, Philippines for the school year 2022-2023. Stratified random sampling was used in this study. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. In stratified random sampling or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is also called proportional random sampling or quota random sampling (Hayes, 2020).

Moreover, the researchers considered the inclusion and exclusion criteria in the selection of the respondents of the study. The teacher respondents were the regular teachers among public elementary schools in Region XI whose plantilla numbers were in the Department of Education. These teachers were MTB-MLE teachers. Teachers were willing to submit themselves and were permitted by their school heads to undergo the survey to be conducted. Those teachers who voluntarily agreed with the informed consent were included in the survey, hence, teachers who clearly confessed their denial were excluded from the study. This study excluded those teachers coming from the private schools. Further, the researcher considered teachers who decided to withdraw or back out during the actual administration of the survey questionnaires.

The modified survey questionnaire used in this study was made up of four parts which are anchored from an adapted questionnaire, re: organizational climate, self-efficacy, work tasks motivation and pedagogical competence. These questionnaires were modified and subjected for validation by experts. The first draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research adviser for comments, suggestions and recommendations to improve its presentation with the corrections to be included and integrated. The final copies were submitted to panel of experts for refinement. The final revision was made by incorporating the corrections, comments and suggestions given by the expert validators before the gathering of data. The consolidated results from the experts obtained an average weighted mean of 4.71 which has a verbal description of excellent. Further, before the administration of the research instrument, a pilot testing was done to selected teachers who were not the respondents of the study. The survey questionnaire for the pilot test was subjected to the reliability testing to establish using Internal Consistency Method. This was the most appropriate method to use since the test contains dichotomously scored items which the examinee either passes or fails in an item. The computed reliability of the instrument was 0.970 for organizational climate questionnaire, 0.980 for self-efficacy questionnaire, 0.960 for work tasks motivation questionnaire, and 0.985 for pedagogical competence questionnaire using Cronbach Alpha.

The questionnaire for organizational climate was adapted from Hoy, Smith, & Sweetland (2002) with the following indicators: institutional vulnerability, collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour, and achievement press.

Further, the questionnaire for self-efficacy of teachers was adapted from Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2010) with the following indicators: instruction, adapting instruction to individual needs, motivating students, maintaining discipline, cooperating with colleagues and parents, and coping with change.

Also, the questionnaire for work task motivation of teachers was adapted from Fernet et al. (2008) with the following indicators: intrinsic motivation, identified regulation, introjected regulation, external regulation and amotivation.

Moreover, the questionnaire for the pedagogical competence of mother tongue teachers was adapted from Mata (2014) with the following indicators: competence to assure the functionality of the educational process, ability to design curriculum, capacity to establish the finalities of education, competence in the use of specific teaching strategies, ability to design the teaching activity, and competence to use the specific assessment strategies.

Furthermore, the quantitative, non-experimental design of research using correlational technique was used in this study. Correlational technique is a non-experimental design, where researcher studies the correlation between variables in a normal setting without manipulation or control. In correlational studies, the researchers examine the strength of relationships among variables by looking into how change in one variable is linked with change in the other variable. Generally, correlational method have independent and dependent variables, but the effect of independent variable is seen on dependent variable without manipulating the independent variable (Creswell, 2002).

Likewise, this study used Structural Equation Modeling. According to Lomax & Li (2013), this method combines factor analysis with path analysis to test theoretical relations among latent variables. Here models can range from simple to complex in nature in that any number of variables of any type can be involved (i.e., observed, latent, independent, and/or dependent variables). The incorporation of factor analysis in structural equation modeling allows the researcher to use multiple measures of each latent variable instead of a single measure, thereby enabling better measurement conditions (i.e., reliability and validity) than with a single measure.

Structural equation modeling (SEM) is a powerful, multivariate technique found increasingly in scientific investigations to test and evaluate multivariate causal relationships. Further, SEM includes the statistical method of path analysis. Path analysis, on the other hand, had its beginning in biometrics and aimed to find the causal relationship among variables by creating a path diagram (Wright, 1921). The path analysis in earlier econometrics was presented with simultaneous equations (Haavelmo, 1943).

Likewise, path analysis was developed to quantify the relationships among multiple variables (Wright, 1921). It was the early name for SEM before there were latent variables, and was very powerful in testing and developing the structural hypothesis with both indirect and direct causal effects. However, the two effects have recently been synonymized. Path analysis can explain the causal relationships among variables. A common function of path analysis is mediation, which assumes that a variable can influence an outcome directly and indirectly through another variable (Fan et al., 2016).

Moreover, path analysis provides a useful framework for specifying and assessing hypothesized causal relations among sets of measured variables (Hancock and Schoonen, 2015). Stage, Carter, and Nora (2004) evaluated the use of path analyses in education researches and identified the aim of path analysis as to give an estimation of the magnitude and significance of hypothesized causal connections among sets of variables displayed through the use of path diagrams.

This method was used to measure the relationship of organizational climate, self-efficacy, work tasks motivation to the pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers among public elementary in Region XI, Philippines. Davao Region, designated as Region XI, is located in the southeastern portion of the island of Mindanao. It is bounded on the north by the provinces of Surigao del Sur, Agusan del Sur, and Bukidnon, on the east by the Philippine Sea, and on the west by the Central Mindanao provinces. It is composed of five provinces – Davao del Sur, Davao del Norte, Davao Oriental, Davao Occidental and Compostela Valley. It also boasts of six cities – Davao, Tagum, Island Garden City of Samal, Panabo, Mati and Digos – that continue to showcase a vibrant investment climate because of their improving competitiveness.

In the collection of data, the researcher asked permission from the Regional Director of DepEd-Region XI, then to the different Schools Division Superintendent. Upon their approval, the researcher then asked permission to the District Supervisors of each chosen District, and to the School Heads concerned, to allow the researcher to conduct the study to the 400 teachers. Upon the approval, the researcher personally distributed and administered the research instruments to ensure 100 percent retrieval of the questionnaires.

The Competence Motivation Theory of White (1959) was used to test the hypothesized models and determine the best fit model for the pedagogical competence among Mother Tongue Based Multilingual teachers.

During the administration of the survey questionnaire, the researcher made sure that the classes were interrupted. During the administration of questionnaire, the possible questions and clarifications of the respondents were personally addressed to the researcher. After the respondents had completely answered the necessary data needed in the questionnaire, the researcher retrieved all the questionnaires administered to the respondents. Then, a Certificate of Appearance was secured from the School Head concerned to

vouch that the researcher honestly collected the data from the research respondents of the study. After the successful retrieval of the questionnaires, the data were collated and tabulated. Then, appropriate statistical tools were employed to derive the necessary data for interpretation and further analysis.

The following statistical tools were used in interpreting the data collated. Mean was used to describe the level of organizational climate, self-efficacy, work tasks motivation and pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers in answer to sub-problems 1 to 4. Pearson r was used to determine the significance of the relationship between pedagogical competence and the independent variables (organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation) in answer to sub-problem 5. Lastly, Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used to test the hypothesized models and determine the best fit model for the pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers among public elementary schools.

In the conduct of this study especially before the data were gathered, ethical issues and considerations were dealt. The researcher had undergone evaluation conducted by the members of ethics review committee. After several review process, this study was marked as passed and approved by the UM Ethics Review Committee (UMERC).

In terms of voluntary participations, the researcher ensured that the participation of the respondents was completely voluntary and anonymous to protect their privacy and information was given whenever the respondents will not understand, before deciding whether to participate or not in the study.

To ensure privacy and confidentiality, the records of this study were confidential as far as permitted by law. Any identifiable information which was obtained in connection with this study remained confidential, except if necessary to protect the respondents' rights or welfare. The researcher resisted the release of information about their participation to people who were not connected with the study. When the results of the study would be published or discussed in conference, no identifiable information would be used. Thus, this research adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012 which protected the teachers from unauthorized processing of their private or identifiable information or guarantee them that their response cannot be traced back to its real sources to protect their identity.

Further, the respondents' name did appear anywhere and no one except the researcher knew about respondents' specific answers. In line with the purpose of protecting the rights of the study participants all the information gather from this study were kept private and confidential.

Also, informed consent was secured from all the respondents involved in the study. The researcher conducted a detailed and comprehensive explanation regarding the purpose of the study to the respondents. The researcher ensured that the condition of the consent was a voluntary choice. The respondents had the sufficient information and adequate understanding of both the proposed research and the implications of their participation in the study in such a way that the results will be utilized by the administrators for whatever purpose this may serve them best. The most important thing considered was that the form must bear the signature of the respondent which implies that he/she participated in the study voluntarily. Moreover, the respondents' personal and private information that were required in the study were treated with utmost care and were kept strictly confidential in accordance to the RA 10173 or Data Privacy Act of 2012 which ensured that all personal data shared were safeguarded and protected.

In terms of recruitment, the researcher ensured the appropriateness of identified recruiting parties and conducted a review of level of risks and measures to mitigate these risks (including physical, psychological and social economic. The possible discomforts that were encountered by the respondents during the survey were managed by the recruiting parties especially the researcher. The researcher was assisted by the school heads and teachers in meeting the number of respondents in the study.

As to risks, benefits, and safety, this research did not involve high risk situation that the population may experience in the area of physical, psychological, or socioeconomic concerns. It protected and secured the rights of the individuals in the study. Likewise, with the result of this study, the researcher yielded a generalizable knowledge about the condition of school employees especially the teachers. The results of this study can help the teachers since the findings of this study will give them new information about their work and their selves. Further, in the conduct of this research, the teacher respondents received tangible benefits such as a simple token from the researcher.

Moreover, the safety of the respondents was ensured using pseudonyms throughout the conduct of the research to protect their identities. Also, the data which were gathered from the survey were kept confidential and were utilized to verify findings of the study. Further, the researcher ensured health protocols amid COVID-19 pandemic during the seeking of organization's permission and approval as well as during the administration of survey questionnaires. To ensure health safety of everyone involved in the study, the researcher explicitly declared adherence to the COVID-19 protocol from the IATF and local ordinances.

In terms of the avoidance of plagiarism, the researcher had undergone the turn-it-in software to ensure that no trace/evidence of misrepresentation of someone else's work as his own. The researcher made sure that the correct and accurate way of citing ideas from other writers and scholars was fully observed. To be able to do this, this paper had undergone grammar checking via Grammarly software. As this study was based on several existing studies, the researcher made sure that he did not make any tale from his literature. Thus, all the information presented were carefully written and cited. All sources used in this study came from reliable journals and other scholarly works. This research complied with the citation rules set forth of APA 7th edition citation format hence there was no

misrepresentation of work or alterations of any data gathered in the study. The data and information obtained were presented in the most accurate way of writing. Hence, no making up of data and/or results, or purposefully putting forward conclusions that were not accurate. No inconsistency with the existing literature among the information was included in manuscript. In the same manner, falsification was also taken into consideration in which no trace of purposefully misrepresenting the work to fit a model or theoretical expectation. No evidence of over claiming or exaggerations.

Additionally, since the researcher is a public school teacher from the intended research locale there is a conflict of interest (COI). Thus, the researcher ensured to clearly eliminate the COI such as not conducting survey to his peers and colleagues. Further, there was no set of conditions in which a professional judgment concerning primary interest such as the respondents' welfare or the validity of the research tends to be influenced by a secondary interest such as financial or academic gains or recognitions. The writings in this paper did not utilize any form of untruthfulness to harm the welfare of the respondents. All the information written were checked and validated by the panel of experts. Moreover, deceit was also avoided in which evidence that the benefit of misleading the respondents outweigh any potential harm to them.

In addition, the permission from the schools was ensured by the researcher. The researcher expressed getting a written permission from the organization in which the research had undertaken or the location in which the data were collected. When getting written permission, the researcher talked to the School Division Superintendent and concerned School Heads to give the permission sought and that the activities were organized well in advance. Also, the survey questionnaires utilized in this study were clear and comprehensible; the researcher made sure that the respondents were fully aware of the benefits the school may get from the study though an informed consent. Thus, the survey was conducted with the approval of the concerned school authorities as well as the permission of the respondents themselves.

Lastly, this study considered authorship qualifications in conduct of the study. The researcher together with the help and guidance of the research adviser substantially contributed to the conception and design, or acquisition of data, or analysis and interpretation of data. The researcher and adviser collaboratively drafted the article and revise it critically for important intellectual content. Both will contribute to the study leading to the publication of the research.

Results and Discussion

Presented in this section are the data and analysis of findings based on the data collated from the research instruments used in the study to determine the model best fits the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers among public elementary schools in Region XI, Philippines. Interpretations of results were engaged in the following subheadings: the level of organizational climate of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, the level of self-efficacy of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, the level of work tasks motivation of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, the level of pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, the significance on the relationship between organizational climate and pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers; the significance on the relationship between self-efficacy and pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, the significance on the relationship between work tasks motivation and pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers; and goodness of fit measures of the three path analysis models.

Level of Organizational Climate of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers

The first objective of this study was to determine the level of organizational climate among public elementary schools as perceived by the mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. The level of organizational climate among public elementary schools is in terms of institutional vulnerability, collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour, and achievement press. Shown in Table 1 are the data on the level of organizational climate among public elementary schools.

Table 1. *Level of Organizational Climate of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
institutional vulnerability	0.768	3.46	high
collegial leadership	0.715	4.18	high
professional teacher behavior	0.618	4.27	very high
achievement press	0.651	3.96	high
Overall	0.539	3.97	high

The level of organizational climate among public elementary schools gets an overall mean of 3.97 or high, with a standard deviation of 0.539. This means that the organizational climate among public elementary schools, as perceived by the teachers, was oftentimes manifested.

From this result, of the four domains of organizational climate among public elementary schools, the professional teacher behavior has the highest mean score of 4.27 or very high followed by collegial leadership with a mean score of 4.18 or high, achievement press, and institutional vulnerability, which gained mean scores of 3.96 and 3.46 respectively, and can be described as high.

The high level of organizational climate of the mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers is due to the high ratings of teacher respondents on institutional vulnerability, collegial leadership, professional teacher behavior, and achievement press. Data implies that the mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers perceived their schools as having positive organizational climate where their experience a school environment and value systems that influences their teaching behaviors at work. This is in consonance with the avowal of several authors (Ceyda & Sevinc, 2012; Ozden, 2014; Taymaz, 2013) which states that positive climate is an important concept that will facilitate the success and welfare level we desire to see in schools. There are important responsibilities for school members in building an environment where they want to be a part of, and where mutual sincerity, trust and respect exist.

Among the four domains of the organizational climate in schools, professional teacher behavior got the highest mean which is followed by collegial leadership, achievement press and institutional vulnerability. The very high level of professional teacher behavior indicates that the mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers see everyone displaying high level of professionalism in terms of their interactions with co-teachers and students in school. They show helping and cooperative behaviors. They respect others' competence. They exercise professional judgment and perform their job functions with enthusiasm especially committed to help students in learning. This finding affirmed the studies of various authors (Lewis, 2021; Lyon, 2021; Quines & Cabaron, 2022; Ramey, 2020) which mentioned that that professional teacher behavior is marked by respect for colleague competence, commitment to students, autonomous judgment, and cooperation and support of colleagues.

Moreover, the high level of collegial leadership as perceived by mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers see their school heads as fair, friendly, and approachable. School heads are seen to be willing to make changes based on the suggestions and ideas of others. School heads maintain definite standards of teacher performance and make these clear to all teachers by clearly explaining what is expected of them. This is aligned with the proposition of some authors (Lyons, 2021; Nichols, 2019; O'Donnell Jr, 2018; Turner, 2018) which affirmed that high level of collegial leadership is manifested as school leaders display leadership behavior directed toward meeting both social needs of the faculty and achieving the goals of the school. The principal treats teachers as colleagues, is open, egalitarian, and friendly, but at the same time sets clear teacher expectations and standards of performance.

In addition, the high level of achievement press indicates school and academic achievement is being recognized and acknowledge by both students and parents in school. Students try hard to set goals and get higher academic performance. Also, parents exert pressure to maintain high standards of learning among students. This is consonance with the contention of several studies (Dahlkamp et al., 2017; Ghavifekr & Pillai, 2016; Malloy & Leithwood, 2017) which pointed that high level of achievement press in school is realized when high but achievable academic standards and goals are set. Students persist, strive to achieve, and are respected by both students and teachers for their academic success. Parents, teachers, and the principal all exert pressure for high standards and school improvement.

Lastly, the high of institutional vulnerability as perceived by mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers implies that the school improvement decisions can be influenced by parents and community. The teachers and school heads respond to community and parents' concerns and needs. This further means that the school is exposed to outside pressures. This confirmed the idea of some authors (Bobba, 2022; Quines & Cabaron, 2022; Ramey, 2020) which explained that high level institutional vulnerability means that the school is susceptible to a few vocal parents and citizen groups. High vulnerability suggests that both teachers and principals are exposed and put on the defensive.

Level of Self-Efficacy of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers

The second objective was to determine the level of self-efficacy of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, which was measured through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators: instruction, adapting instruction to individual needs, motivating student, maintaining discipline, cooperating with colleagues and parents, and coping with change. Shown in Table 2 are the data on the level of self-efficacy of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. Computations yielded a grand mean of 4.32 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.558, and this indicates that the self-efficacy of teachers is always manifested.

Table 2. *Level of Self-Efficacy of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Instruction	0.608	4.45	very high
adapting instruction to individual needs	0.587	4.33	very high
motivating students	0.616	4.34	very high
maintaining discipline	0.615	4.26	very high
cooperating with colleagues and parents	0.668	4.26	very high
coping with change	0.653	4.25	very high
Overall	0.558	4.32	very high

Data reveals that the domain of self-efficacy of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers that yielded the highest mean score, as shown in Table 2, is instruction with a mean rating of 4.45 or very high followed by motivating students with a mean score of 4.34 or very high, and adapting instruction to individual needs with a mean score of 4.33 or very high. Then this is followed by maintaining discipline and cooperating with colleagues and parents which both gained a mean score of 4.26 or very high. Lastly, the lowest indicator, albeit very high is the coping with change which a got a mean score of 4.25.

The very high level of self-efficacy of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers is due to the very high ratings of teacher respondents on instruction, adapting instruction to individual needs, motivating student, maintaining discipline, cooperating with colleagues and parents, and coping with change. Data implies that the mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers display the ability in delivering effective instruction especially in adapting learning tasks that suits the varied levels of students' skills and capabilities. They are good in terms of motivating learners to learn and at the same time manage student behaviors and discipline inside the classroom. They have skills in connecting with parents and co-teachers especially when managing changes in the school curriculum. This result expanded the idea of some authors (Bandura, 2016; Goddard et al., 2018) which stated that teachers with high level of self-efficacy execute courses of action required to produce given attainments. Teachers with efficacy are persistent in their effort to meet these goals and tasks at work even if these are challenging goals due to existing changes. In addition, Skaalvik & Skaalvik (2018) mentioned that those teachers who have high level of self-efficacy perceive themselves to have better teaching ability.

Among the six domains of self-efficacy of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, instruction yielded the highest mean which implies that mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers provide good guidance and instruction to all students regardless of their ability. This is in parallel with the statement of several authors (Avanzi et al., 2013; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2010) which explained that teachers with high level of self-efficacy in instruction expect to be able to effectively instruct students, explain subject matter, and answer questions to improve students' understanding.

Further, the very high level of teachers' self-efficacy in terms of motivating students means that mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers get all students in class to be interested, work hard, and do their best even when working with difficult tasks. This supported the proposition of several authors (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2007; Solheim et al., 2018) which revealed that optimal learning is dependent on student motivation. Motivating students is therefore an important task for all teachers. Teacher self-efficacy for motivating students can be seen how they rekindle the desire to learn even among the lowest-achieving students.

Similarly, the very high level of teachers' self-efficacy in terms of adapting instruction to individual needs indicates that mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers organize students' tasks to adapt instruction and assignment to individual needs. These teachers provide genuine challenge to diverse learners with different levels of ability. This is in congruence with some researchers (Al-Alwan & Mahasneh, 2014; Hassan & Ibourk, 2021; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2007) which postulated that the self-efficacy of teachers in terms of adapting instruction to individual students' needs is seen as a key element in the movement toward inclusive education. Teachers with high level of self-efficacy in terms of adapting instruction to individual students' needs perceive the goal to be inclusive as extremely demanding and that many teachers are doing its best to address the diversity of students' needs and abilities. One example is that they provide realistic challenge for all students even in mixed ability classes.

Also, data revealed very high level of teachers' self-efficacy in terms of maintaining discipline which implies that mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers maintain discipline of students by controlling students' aggressive behaviors and getting all students to practice politeness and respect towards classmates and teachers. This is in support to the findings of several authors (Elstad & Christophersen, 2017; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2007) that teachers with high self-efficacy in maintaining discipline have the ability to maintain order and discipline. They can get students with behavioral problems to follow classroom rules.

Additionally, the very high level of teachers' self-efficacy in terms of cooperating with colleagues and parents indicates that the mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers collaboratively cooperate well with teachers and parents in finding solutions to problems of students. This is in line with the findings of some studies (Avanzi et al., 2013; Ninković & Knežević Florić, 2018; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2007) which exposed those teachers with high level of self-efficacy in terms of cooperating with colleagues and parents are skillful in terms of cooperating well with most parents and cooperating effectively and constructively with other teachers, for example, in teaching teams. They always have the sense of desire to cooperate with others to solve problems.

Lastly, the very high level of teachers' self-efficacy in terms of coping with change implies that the mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers are successfully managing instruction amidst the changes in the curriculum. They effectively use instructional methods decided by the school to be used. This supported the idea of some authors (Ballantyne & Retell, 2020; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2007) which avowed those teachers with the ability to cope with change effectively manage instruction even if the curriculum is changed and teaching well even if the instructional methods introduced are new to them. They have the sense of desire to adapt oneself to methodological and situational changes.

Level of Work Tasks Motivation of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers

The third objective was to determine the level of work tasks motivation of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers which was measured through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators: intrinsic motivation, identified regulation, introjected regulation, external regulation, and amotivation. Shown in Table 3 are the data on the level of work tasks motivation of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. Computations yielded a grand mean of 4.34 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.570, and this indicates that the work tasks motivation of teachers is oftentimes manifested.

Data shows that the indicator of the work tasks motivation of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers that yielded the highest mean score, as shown in Table 3, is the intrinsic motivation with a mean score of 4.45 or very high followed by identified regulation with a mean score of 4.43 or a very high, introjected regulation with a mean score of 4.42 or very high. Then this is followed

by amotivation, which gained a mean score of 4.36 or very high, and lastly, the lowest indicator is the external regulation, albeit still high, which gained a mean score of 4.05.

Table 3. *Level of Work Tasks Motivation of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
intrinsic motivation	0.620	4.45	very high
identified regulation	0.634	4.43	very high
introjected regulation	0.643	4.42	very high
external regulation	0.690	4.05	high
amotivation	0.614	4.36	very high
Overall	0.570	4.34	very high

The very high level of work tasks motivation of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers is due to the very high ratings of teachers on intrinsic motivation, identified regulation, introjected regulation, external regulation, and amotivation. Data means that mother tongue teachers always felt motivated towards mother tongue language-based instruction. This further implies that teachers feel the pleasure and satisfaction when performing their roles as mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. Mother tongue teachers are highly driven and interested to do their job effectively. This is in parallel with the result of the findings of the study of Lartec et al. (2014) who pointed out that mother tongue teachers need to be motivated in implementing mother tongue language-based instruction. These teachers are emotionally prepared which means they must be motivated for them to effectively teach their learners with the use of mother tongue as the medium of instruction. Also, this substantiates the contention of various authors (Bieg et al., 2011; Kim & Cho, 2014; Recepoglu, 2013) who revealed that teachers should be motivated to teach effectively to accomplish its objective of giving quality learning and training to the learners. The teachers are more committed and involved in their work if they are highly satisfied and motivated.

Furthermore, among the five indicators in the work tasks motivation of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, teacher respondents perceived that intrinsic motivation dominated over the other four indicators, namely: identified regulation, introjected regulation, amotivation, and external regulation. Based on the data, the mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers observed themselves to have high inherent satisfaction towards their work as mother tongue teachers. Teachers are intrinsically motivated towards their job. They feel pleasant and like to do their job since they perceive each task of a mother tongue teacher interesting to do. This indicates that mother tongue teachers are involved in their tasks for the satisfaction and pleasure resulting from executing them. This pursues the assumption of various authors (Fernet et al., 2008; Jarvela & Jarvenoja, 2011; Ofoegbu, 2004) who stipulated those teachers who are intrinsically motivated may be observed to assume a task because of the feeling of accomplishment and self-actualization it offers or satisfaction per se. Also, this finding is similar to the study of Bachore (2014) who revealed that teachers disclosed that they are interested to teach various subjects using mother tongue. Moreover, the result reiterates the idea of various authors (Bieg et al. 2011; Perlman & Piletic, 2012) who pointed out that teachers need inherent determination to be more involved and enjoyed in their tasks.

Moreover, in terms of identified regulation, data revealed very high level which implies that the mother tongue teachers are always motivated to carry out their task because they perceive their tasks as equally important for the academic achievement of the learners. This further means that they see the value of mother tongue instruction especially with how it could improve the learning of the learners. This is in consonance with the statement of Ryan et al. (2011) who stated that teachers become more motivated towards their work when they identify its value and accepts it as one's own. Additionally, this study discloses that teachers raise the idea that they tend to be more driven towards MTB curriculum because they see its advantages especially in attaining salient objectives about improving learners' skills, cognitive abilities, and cultural identity. This finding confirmed the assertion of various authors (Brock-Utne, 2006; Cummins, 2000; Thomas & Collier, 2010; Walter & Dekker, 2011; Wright & Taylor, 1995) who stated that teachers acknowledge the probable benefits of mother tongue instruction for learners such as augmenting learners' academic skills, critical thinking skills and cultural pride.

Further, data showed very high level of introjected regulation, which means that that mother tongue teachers oftentimes feel guilty, bad, and disappointed for not carrying and doing their task as mother tongue instructors. This finding substantiates the confirmation of various authors (Soenens et al., 2012; Verstuyf et al., 2012) who stipulated those teachers having high introjection results to perform their tasks out of internally compelling forces such as infamy and guilt. Consequently, the findings revealed that mother tongue teachers constrain themselves to be excellent in delivering the MTB curriculum because they see possible failures as unacceptable. This implies that MTB teachers wanted to perform better to gain pride and self-confidence in their work. Hence, they feel the ego of having the responsibility to do their task adeptly. This is in line with the statements of Nicholls (1984) and Ryan (1982) who asserted that teachers perform such actions with the feeling of pressure to attain ego-enhancements or pride which means that they do their job to enhance or maintain the feeling of worth or self-image.

On the other hand, there was a very high level of amotivation among mother tongue teachers. This indicates that in some cases they do not see the relevance or purpose of doing the task of a mother tongue teacher which means that every so often they do not realize the reason anymore even if they used to know why they were doing the task of a mother tongue teacher. Relatively, some possible reasons for MTB teachers' lack of motivation are the inadequate instructional materials and perceived competence to teach the mother tongue

which is being used in the instruction. This in parallel with the view of Lartec et al. (2014) who said that some reasons for mother tongue teachers' low motivation in the Philippines are some problems encountered by them such as scarcity of books written in mother tongue, lack of vocabulary, and inadequate teacher-training. Similarly, the finding is in conjunction with the assertion of diverse authors (Deci & Ryan 1985; Deci et al. 1991; Vallerand & Bissonnette 1992; Vallerand et al. 1992; Frederick & Ryan, 1995) who claimed that amotivated teachers sometimes withdraw their effort in fulfilling their task because of loss of focus and views of incompetence.

Lastly, mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers revealed high level of external regulation. This implies that they perceived themselves to have been doing the tasks as mother tongue teachers because their work demands it. This implies that mother tongue teachers do their tasks because the school requires them. This expanded the idea of several authors (Kim & Cho, 2014; Ryan et al., 1994) who pointed out that teachers who have high external regulation of motivation do school tasks because of external pressures. This means that they are obliged to fulfill school policies and implemented curriculum. Correspondingly, it was found out that mother tongue teachers are oftentimes driven to perform their duties because of rewards and compensation. This can be associated with the contention of various authors (Demir, 2011; Ofoegbu, 2004) in their view than extrinsically motivated teachers may perform their tasks to gain rewards like salary. Additionally, the data make known that introjected regulation is in the high level. This indicates that mother tongue teachers oftentimes feel guilty, bad, and disappointed for not carrying and doing their task as mother tongue instructors. This finding substantiates the confirmation of various authors (Soenens et al., 2012; Verstuyf et al., 2012) who stipulated those teachers having high introjection results to perform their tasks out of internally compelling forces such as infamy and guilt.

Level of Pedagogical Competence of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers

The fourth objective was to determine level of pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers with the following indicators: competence to assure the functionality of the educational process, ability to design curriculum, capacity to establish the finalities of education, competence in the use specific teaching strategies, ability to design the teaching activity, and competence to use the specific assessment strategies. Shown in Table 4 are the data on the level of pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. Computations yielded a grand mean of 4.27 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.575, and this indicates that the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers is always manifested.

From this result, the indicator of pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers that yielded the highest mean score, as shown in Table 4, is competence to assure the functionality of the educational process with a mean score of 4.36 or very high followed by competence in the use specific teaching strategies ranked as the second-highest indicator with a mean score of 4.31 or very high. Then this is followed by ability to design curriculum and competence to use the specific assessment strategies which gained the mean scores of 4.26. Also, other indicators such as capacity to establish the finalities of education and ability to design the teaching activity got the mean scores of 4.24 and 4.21, respectively which can be interpreted as very high.

Table 4. *Level of Pedagogical Competence of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
competence to assure the functionality of the educational process	0.653	4.36	very high
ability to design curriculum	0.626	4.26	very high
capacity to establish the finalities of education	0.586	4.24	very high
competence in the use specific teaching strategies	0.649	4.31	very high
ability to design the teaching activity	0.617	4.21	very high
competence to use the specific assessment strategies	0.652	4.26	very high
Overall	0.575	4.27	very high

The very high level of pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers is due to the very high rating given by the teacher respondents on competence to assure the functionality of the educational process, ability to design curriculum, capacity to establish the finalities of education, competence in the use specific teaching strategies, ability to design the teaching activity, and competence to use the specific assessment strategies.

Data implies that mother tongue teachers can design cultural and authentic-based classroom learning experiences and activities for mother tongue language learning. They could design curriculum where they formulate concrete objectives for language learning. Also, they have the competence to use specific assessment strategies to gauge learners' language acquisition. Moreover, this corresponds to the study of various authors (Benson et al., 2010; Lartec et al., 2014; Mata, 2014) who claimed that mother tongue teachers must acquire pedagogical competence in the implementation of mother tongue instruction in which they expertly apply innovative teaching strategies during instruction and who have rich background about the culture and language of the mother tongue learners.

In conjunction, this also validates the assertion of some authors (Madhavaram & Laverie, 2010; Mata, 2014; Ryegard, 2010) who emphasized that pedagogical competence among mother tongue teachers is very crucial in implementing the mother tongue-based instruction. Mother tongue teachers should acquire pedagogical competence in MTB instruction which requires them to have set of attitudes, skills, and knowledge to effectively affect the learners' learning.

In the same vein, the overall result substantiates the idea of various authors (Ingram, 2007; Liddicoat et al., 2005; Mata, 2014; Oser & Renold, 2006) who said that there is a need for competent teachers who desired for the implementation of mother-tongue teaching.

These teachers must have both established advanced language competences and concrete methodological-didactic competencies.

In addition, among the six indicators in pedagogical competence of mother tongue teachers, respondents perceived that competence to assure the functionality of the educational process dominated over the other five indicators, namely: competence in the use specific teaching strategies, ability to design curriculum, competence to use the specific assessment strategies, capacity to establish the finalities of education, and ability to design the teaching activity.

The very high level of teachers' competence to assure the functionality of the educational process means that that mother tongue teachers develop the cognitive, ethical, creative, physical, and technological components of education into the mother tongue pedagogy. This corroborates with the idea of various authors (Mata, 2014; Ranaweer, 1990; Rassekh & Vaideanu, 1987) who revealed that it is important for teachers to align mother tongue curriculum contents with the intellectual and physical needs and abilities of learners.

In connection, the teachers also revealed that they facilitate the compliance of principles of education into mother tongue instruction such as utilizing authentic classroom learning activities and experiences by using the learners' first language and culture in real-world contexts. This finding demonstrates the statement of some authors (Allen, 2014; Clementi & Terrill, 2013) who declared that it is important for teachers to integrate culture in language activities and tasks to provide a context and a real-life purpose for language.

Also, the very high level of competence in the use specific teaching strategies among mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers implies that they integrate specific lesson or instructional tools to encourage learners to use their mother tongue in genuine situations. This is in connection with the statement of Ritchhart (2002) who states that mother tongue teachers should employ teaching tools that will allow and encourage the learners to use their mother tongue to access the curriculum. Such as they may complete lesson tasks and assessments in their mother tongue, and they are stimulated to share their knowledge and growth with their parents and other people in the community using their mother tongue.

Further, in addition with the above result, teachers have usually combined pair practice and individual learning in the mother tongue instruction. Congruent to this finding is the declaration of various authors (Haines, 1995; Harmer, 2001; Nolasco & Arthur, 1988) who stated that even in mother tongue instruction teachers should know how to employ paired work with individual learning since it has advantage to teaching. It is said that it gives learners more time for conversation, cooperation, and autonomy. It also allows for individual differences in learning style.

More so, in terms of teachers' ability to design curriculum, the very high rating of teachers indicates that MTB teachers always apply the types of curricula developed at the national level which means to show that they adopt the K-12 curriculum which incorporates the use of mother tongue especially in the Grades 1 -3. In addition, the result shows that MTB teachers are active in selecting relevant curricular documents or references for mother tongue pedagogy. This confirms the assertion of various authors (MacKenzie, 2010; Mackenzie & Walker, 2015) who emphasized that concerned mother tongue teachers should back up culturally contextualized curriculum in the MTB instruction with suitable and appropriate curriculum materials which are written in mother tongue that is relevant to students.

In addition, the very high level of competence to use the specific assessment strategies of MTB teachers signifies that they perceived themselves having the ability to construct diagnostic, formative, and summative assessments to assess and rate the performance of mother tongue learners. This is in parallel to the study of Mata (2014) who revealed that mother tongue teachers considered that the most imperative pedagogical factor was using specific methods of knowledge assessment to measure the abilities and skills of learners in first language acquisition.

In conjunction with the above result, the data also disclosed that in mother tongue curriculum, the mother tongue teachers always incorporate assessment methods for the attitudes, values, and behaviors of learners towards mother tongue acquisition. This in line with the statement of Bachore (2014) who pointed out that teachers need to assess the learners' perception and attitudes towards mother tongue instruction to meet the classroom demands.

Likewise, the very high level of capacity to establish the finalities of education of MTB teachers. The data revealed aspects of such capacity as they adeptly consider important competencies for their lesson. This indicates that they can formulate concrete lesson objectives for language and literature lessons. This finding corroborates with the finding of the study of various authors (Kelly et al., 2004; Mata, 2014; Tulasiewicz & Adams, 2005) who revealed that mother tongue teachers should have enough capacity to create substantial objectives or outcomes for MTB lessons.

Lastly, there was a very high level of ability to design the teaching activity of MTB teachers. This indicates that mother tongue teachers oftentimes design activities that give learners the opportunities to use their first language outside the school. Likewise, the result indicates that the mother tongue teachers have ability to design plan for various types of MTB lessons. Apparently, they elaborate the annual and periodical design for MTB language and literature lessons.

Contentions of various authors (Mata, 2014; North, 2009; Wang, 2001) are in connection with this finding as they affirmed that mother tongue teachers should have the ability to design effective instructional plans that will assist the language acquisition and learning of MTB learners. Likewise, it confirms the idea that mother tongue teachers need to plan task-based activities that allow learners to use their mother tongue in contextualized situations.

Significance on the Relationship between Organizational Climate and Pedagogical Competence of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers

One important purpose of this study was to determine whether organizational climate has a significant relationship with the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. The results of the computations are shown in Table 5. As shown in the table, the overall r-value on the correlation between the level of organizational climate and the level pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers is 0.619 with $p < 0.05$, which means that organizational climate is significantly associated with the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Further, when the domains of organizational climate such as the institutional vulnerability, collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour, and achievement press were correlated to the overall pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, results of the computation yielded the r-values of 0.250, 0.481, 0.689, and 0.576 with the p-values of less than 0.05, respectively, which can be all interpreted as significant.

These factors are significantly related to the domains of pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, such as the competence to assure the functionality of the educational process, ability to design curriculum, capacity to establish the finalities of education, competence in the use specific teaching strategies, ability to design the teaching activity, and competence to use the specific assessment strategies.

Table 5. Significance on the Relationship between Organizational Climate and Pedagogical Competence of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers

Organizational Climate	Pedagogical Competence of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers						Overall
	competence to assure the functionality of the educational process	ability to design curriculum	capacity to establish the finalities of education	competence in the use specific teaching strategies	ability to design the teaching activity	competence to use the specific assessment strategies	
institutional vulnerability	.246* (0.000)	.317* (0.000)	.277* (0.000)	.176* (0.001)	.268* (0.000)	.093 (0.092)	.250* (0.000)
collegial leadership	.433* (0.000)	.409* (0.000)	.457* (0.000)	.413* (0.000)	.421* (0.000)	.502* (0.000)	.481* (0.000)
professional teacher behavior	.692* (0.000)	.635* (0.000)	.666* (0.000)	.588* (0.000)	.564* (0.000)	.629* (0.000)	.689* (0.000)
achievement press	.574* (0.000)	.522* (0.000)	.534* (0.000)	.480* (0.000)	.458* (0.000)	.586* (0.000)	.576* (0.000)
Overall	.603* (0.000)	.588* (0.000)	.601* (0.000)	.512* (0.000)	.534* (0.000)	.556* (0.000)	.619* (0.000)

Data showed that organizational climate is significantly associated with the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. This supported the proposition of Selamat, Samsu & Kamalu (2013) specifically exposed the significant relationship between the climate of the workplace and pedagogical competence or performance of teachers. The workplace climate was found to be a significant factor that could affect teachers’ job performance. In addition, other researchers (Hakim, Sa’ud, Komariah & Sunaengsih, 2017; Selamat, Samsu & Kamalu, 2013) stated that climate of the school affects the pedagogical competence or performance of teachers. School climates have positive and significant influence upon teachers’ teaching performance.

Significance on the Relationship Between Self-Efficacy and Pedagogical Competence of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers

Another purpose of this study was to determine whether self-efficacy has a significant relationship with the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. The results of the computations are shown in Table 6. As shown in the table, the overall r-value on the correlation between the level of self-efficacy and the level pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers is 0.814 with $p < 0.05$, which means that the self-efficacy is significantly associated with the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Further, when the domains of self-efficacy such as the instruction, adapting instruction to individual needs, motivating student, maintaining discipline, cooperating with colleagues and parents, and coping with change were correlated to the overall pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, results of the computation yielded the r-values of 0.829, 0.743, 0.711, 0.665, 0.662, 0.764, and 0.814 with the p-values of less than 0.05, respectively, which can be all interpreted as significant.

These factors are significantly related to the domains of pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, such as the competence to assure the functionality of the educational process, ability to design curriculum, capacity to establish the finalities of education, competence in the use specific teaching strategies, ability to design the teaching activity, and competence to use the specific assessment strategies.

Table 6. Significance on the Relationship Between Self-Efficacy and Pedagogical Competence of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers

Self-Efficacy of Teachers	Pedagogical Competence of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers						Overall
	competence to assure the functionality of the educational process	ability to design curriculum	capacity to establish the finalities of education	competence in the use specific teaching strategies	ability to design the teaching activity	competence to use the specific assessment strategies	
Instruction	.809* (0.000)	.768* (0.000)	.775* (0.000)	.732* (0.000)	.693* (0.000)	.758* (0.000)	.829* (0.000)
adapting instruction to individual needs	.710* (0.000)	.709* (0.000)	.760* (0.000)	.629* (0.000)	.660* (0.000)	.611* (0.000)	.743* (0.000)
motivating students	.686* (0.000)	.691* (0.000)	.729* (0.000)	.553* (0.000)	.640* (0.000)	.606* (0.000)	.711* (0.000)
maintaining discipline	.631* (0.000)	.659* (0.000)	.647* (0.000)	.487* (0.000)	.553* (0.000)	.667* (0.000)	.665* (0.000)
cooperating with colleagues and parents	.679* (0.000)	.510* (0.000)	.712* (0.000)	.552* (0.000)	.637* (0.000)	.550* (0.000)	.662* (0.000)
coping with change	.754* (0.000)	.706* (0.000)	.729* (0.000)	.650* (0.000)	.617* (0.000)	.729* (0.000)	.764* (0.000)
Overall	.795* (0.000)	.751* (0.000)	.811* (0.000)	.671* (0.000)	.708* (0.000)	.730* (0.000)	.814* (0.000)

Data revealed that the self-efficacy is significantly associated with the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. This expanded the views of several authors (Akay & Boz, 2011; Alkan & Erdem, 2012; Cherian & Jacob, 2013; Ogun & Topkaya, 2008; Sahin, 2010) which explained that self-efficacy was seen to be a factor influencing the performance of individuals at workplace and the mechanism by which self-efficacy of an individual determines his/her work-related performance. Self-efficacy was associated with the pedagogical competence of teachers. There is a positive relationship between self-efficacy scores and professional competency scores of teachers.

Significance on the Relationship Between Work Tasks Motivation and Pedagogical Competence of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers

This present study also aimed to determine whether work tasks motivation has a significant relationship with the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. The results of the computations are shown in Table 7. As shown in the table, the overall r-value on the correlation between the level of work tasks motivation and the level pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers is 0.857 with $p < 0.05$, which means that the work tasks motivation is significantly associated with the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

In addition, when the domains of work tasks motivation such as the intrinsic motivation, identified regulation, introjected regulation, external regulation, and amotivation were correlated to the overall pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, results of the computation yielded the r-values of 0.795, 0.820, 0.804, 0.603, 0.811, and 0.857 with the p-values of less than 0.05, respectively, which can be all interpreted as significant. These factors are significantly related to the domains of pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, such as the competence to assure the functionality of the educational process, ability to design curriculum, capacity to establish the finalities of education, competence in the use specific teaching strategies, ability to design the teaching activity, and competence to use the specific assessment strategies.

Data exposed that work tasks motivation is significantly associated with the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. This confirmed the findings of various studies (Davidson, 2005; Mustafa & Othman, 2010; Nadeem, Rana, Lone, Maqbool, Naz & Ali, 2011) which revealed that motivation is one factor that was seen to influence the pedagogical competence of teachers. Teachers with higher level of motivation tend to have greater competence in teaching. Moreover, if teachers experienced a motivating work environment, they tend to have increased teaching competence and performance. This signifies that building the teachers' level of motivation will enhance the instruction framework.

In the same vein, it substantiates the result of the study of Silverio (2016) which pointed out that motivation of mother tongue teachers plays as a significant aspect in augmenting their pedagogical competence particularly on their competence to assure the quality and functionality of the MTB curriculum and the competence to utilize important MTB teaching strategies and assessment. Thus, MTB

Filipino teachers need a particular motivation in such a way that the greater the level of motivation they have, the higher will be their job performance or competence specifically with their ability to plan MTB pedagogy and with their capacity to formulating authentic outcomes for language learning.

Table 7. Significance on the Relationship Between Work Tasks Motivation and Pedagogical Competence of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers

Work Tasks Motivation	Pedagogical Competence of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Teachers						Overall
	competence to assure the functionality of the educational process	ability to design curriculum	capacity to establish the finalities of education	competence in the use specific teaching strategies	ability to design the teaching activity	competence to use the specific assessment strategies	
intrinsic motivation	.783* (0.000)	.731* (0.000)	.741* (0.000)	.698* (0.000)	.667* (0.000)	.728* (0.000)	.795* (0.000)
identified regulation	.833* (0.000)	.772* (0.000)	.782* (0.000)	.684* (0.000)	.699* (0.000)	.719* (0.000)	.820* (0.000)
introjected regulation	.842* (0.000)	.744* (0.000)	.765* (0.000)	.688* (0.000)	.678* (0.000)	.686* (0.000)	.804* (0.000)
external regulation	.587* (0.000)	.612* (0.000)	.628* (0.000)	.445* (0.000)	.568* (0.000)	.471* (0.000)	.603* (0.000)
amotivation	.842* (0.000)	.851* (0.000)	.762* (0.000)	.691* (0.000)	.656* (0.000)	.640* (0.000)	.811* (0.000)
Overall	.869* (0.000)	.830* (0.000)	.824* (0.000)	.824* (0.000)	.716* (0.000)	.732* (0.000)	.857* (0.000)

Best Fit Model Analysis. This part discusses how the best fit model was generated by presenting the three generated models based on the goodness of fit measures using path analysis.

Figure 2. Path Analysis Model 1 in Standardized Solution

Legend: OrgClimate, Organizational Climate; SelfEfficacy, Self-Efficacy; WorkTaskMotivation, Work Task Motivation; PedagogicalComp, Pedagogical Competence

Generated Model 1. Shown in Figure 6 is Hypothesized Model 1 in standardized solution. It is tested model depicting the interrelationships between the latent exogenous variables and its direct causal relation to the endogenous variable pedagogical competence’s findings indicate that both organizational climate and self-efficacy directly contribute to pedagogical competence. Furthermore, there is a significant correlation between organizational climate and work task motivation.

Additionally, organizational climate and work task motivation has an impact on self-efficacy, with these two exogenous variables directly influencing pedagogical competence. In assessing the absolute fit of generated model 1, it can be extracted from the table that Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom (CMIN/DF) of 83.200 provided a poor fit, goodness of Fit Index (GFI) of .900 did not offer a good support for the model, and Root Means Square of Error Approximation (RMSEA) of .500 did not meet the criterion to be reasonably fit. When assessing the comparative fit measures, data revealed the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) was .938, Normed Fit Index (NFI) was .938 and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) was .631 indicating that it did not fall within the acceptable and did not support for the model. Moreover, the P – value .000 was not greater than 0.05 and P- Close (.000) was not higher than 0.05.

Table 8. Goodness of Fit Measures of Path Analysis Model 1

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-Close	> 0.05	.000
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	83.200
P-value	> 0.05	.000
GFI	> 0.95	.900
CFI	> 0.95	.938
NFI	> 0.95	.938
TLI	> 0.95	.631
RMSEA	< 0.05	.500

Legend: CMIN/DF, Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom; NFI, Normed Fit Index; TLI, Tucker-Lewis Index; CFI, Comparative Fit Index; GFI, Goodness of Fit Index; RMSEA, Root Means Square of Error Approximation; Pclose, P of Close Fit; P-value, Probability Level

Overall, Path analysis was a very poor fit model as it failed to pass each of the criteria.

Generated Model 2. A model modification approach (Kline,2005) was warranted by testing the hypothesized model and removing indicator or variable to improve the fit of the data. To apply this approach, reflected in Figure 3 is Hypothesized Model 2 in standardized solution. It is a tested model showing the interrelationships among the three exogenous variables namely; organizational climate, self-efficacy and work task motivation and their relationships on endogenous variable pedagogical competence. Furthermore, it is evident that organizational climate and work task motivation yield substantial influence over pedagogical competence. Also, there is a significant correlation between organizational climate and work task motivation. Additionally, these two exogenous variables namely; organizational climate and work task motivation exhibit a direct influence on self-efficacy. Showing direct effect of organizational climate and work task motivation on pedagogical competence of Mother Tongue Teachers.

Figure 3. Path Analysis Model 2 in Standardized Solution

Legend: OrgClimate, Organizational Climate; SelfEfficacy, Self-Efficacy; WorkTaskMotivation, Work Task Motivation; PedagogicalComp, Pedagogical Competence

Moreover, Table 9 is the Goodness of Fit Measure of Path Analysis Model 2. It had shown significant improvement among indices when compared to Model 1. In analyzing the absolute fit of generated model 2, the indices CMIN/DF manifested from 83.200 to 4.053; RMSEA produced results from .500 to .096. This indicated a poor fit since it did not satisfy the criteria for absolute fit. For comparative fit, it did not pass the GFI from .900 to .994, NFI from .938 to .997 and TLI from .631 to .986. The P-Value from 0.000 to .044 was lesser than 0.05 while the P-Close from .0000 to .136 was higher than 0.05. Hence, Path Analysis Model 2 was a poor fit in totality.

Table 9. Goodness of Fit Measures of Path Analysis Model 2

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-Close	> 0.05	.136
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	4.053
P-value	> 0.05	.044
GFI	> 0.95	.994
CFI	> 0.95	.998
NFI	> 0.95	.997
TLI	> 0.95	.986
RMSEA	< 0.05	.096

Legend: CMIN/DF, Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom; NFI, Normed Fit Index; TLI, Tucker-Lewis Index; CFI, Comparative Fit Index; GFI, Goodness of Fit Index; RMSEA, Root Means Square of Error Approximation; Pclose, P of Close Fit; P-value, Probability Level

Generated Model 3. Lastly, Figure 4 shows the Path Analysis Model 3 in Standardized Solution. This portion provides analysis on the interrelationships among the variables of the study and assessment of model fit. As shown in the Appended Figure 4, the amount of variance explained by the combined influence of organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation on the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers is 74%.

Hence, it can be gleaned that 74% of the variance of the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers can be attributed to the combined influence of organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation of the mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers.

It is a tested model depicting the interrelationships between the latent exogenous variables and its direct causal relation to the endogenous variable pedagogical competence of mother tongue based-multilingual teachers. Furthermore, self-efficacy and work tasks motivation were significantly correlated with pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers. Additionally, organizational climate and work tasks motivation have an impact on self-efficacy, with these two exogenous variables directly influencing pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers. Moreover, the substantial among indices were manifested in Model 3 when compared to Model 2.

Figure 4. Path Analysis Model 3 in Standardized Solution

Legend: OrgClimate, Organizational Climate; SelfEfficacy, Self-Efficacy; WorkTaskMotivation, Work Task Motivation; PedagogicalComp, Pedagogical Competence

It can be instructed from Table 10 that Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom (CMIN/DF) from 4.053 to .041 provided a best fit, Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) from .994 to 1.000 offers a very good support for the model, and Root Means Square of Error Approximation (RMSEA) from .096 to .000 does satisfy the criterion to be reasonably fit. When assessing the comparative fit measures, results revealed that Comparative Fit Index (CFI) was from .998 to 1.000, Normed Fit Index (NFI) was from .997 to 1.000 and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) was from .986 to 1.004; implying that it did meet within the acceptable criteria and provide best support for the model. Moreover, the P-Value from .044 to .840 was greater than 0.05 and P-Close from .136 to .893 was higher than 0.05 and which are all meet within the acceptable ranges.

Model 3 came out as the best fit model satisfying the criteria for the standard-fit as a result of the causal model data fitting using Pearson r, which should be significant. Model 3 has satisfied all these criteria. Thus, there was no need to find another model for testing because it was already found to be the best-fit model among the all the tested models. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no best-fit model was rejected.

Table 10. Goodness of Fit Measures of Path Analysis Model 3

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-Close	> 0.05	.893
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	.041
P-value	> 0.05	.840
GFI	> 0.95	1.000
CFI	> 0.95	1.000
NFI	> 0.95	1.000
TLI	> 0.95	1.004
RMSEA	< 0.05	.000

Legend: CMIN/DF, Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom; NFI, Normed Fit Index; TLI, Tucker-Lewis Index; CFI, Comparative Fit Index; GFI, Goodness of Fit Index; RMSEA, Root Means Square of Error Approximation; Pclose, P of Close Fit; P-value, Probability Level

The results of the study is supported the proposition of Hakim et al. (2017) which revealed that the climate of the school and motivation affects the pedagogical competence or performance of teachers. In any organization, the self-efficacy and work tasks motivation contributes to the pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers. Organizational climate and work tasks motivation are correlated with each other and have impacted the self-efficacy of teachers which has an indirect significant influence on pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers. Hence, these are important factors in increasing teaching competence. Also, it confirmed several studies (Akay & Boz, 2011; Alkan & Erdem, 2012; Cherian & Jacob, 2013; Ogun & Topkaya, 2008; Sahin, 2010) which pointed out that self-efficacy was associated with the pedagogical competence of teachers.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, conclusions were drawn as follows: The descriptive level of the exogenous variables: organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers are high to very high which signifies that these variables are evident and practiced often or most of the time. Meanwhile, the endogenous variable - pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, with a very high descriptive level, signifies that pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers is manifested in all the time.

The significant relationships between organizational climate and pedagogical competence, and between self-efficacy and pedagogical competence as well as between work tasks motivation and pedagogical competence imply that any increase in organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation results in a corresponding increase in the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers.

The structural model indicates the best fit model for the pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers as proven by the summary of the goodness of fit satisfying all the indices for a path model analysis.

The significant direct effect of self-efficacy and work tasks motivation on the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers implies that pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers is influenced by their self-efficacy and work tasks motivation as teachers. Though the other one exogenous variable, organizational climate, do not directly influence the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. Though the other one exogenous variable, organizational climate, do not directly influence the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers, its significant direct effects on the self-efficacy denote that, despite the weight of self-efficacy on teachers' pedagogical competence, it still needs the influence of organizational climate to boost its effect.

Finally, findings showed that Model 3 came out as the best-fit path model that predicts the pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers. The model showed that self-efficacy and work tasks motivation have direct effect on pedagogical competence while organizational climate has indirect effect on pedagogical competence of MTB-MLE teachers. This implies that schools may enhance their professional development programs by focusing on teachers' ability in MTB-MLE instruction.

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are suggested. It was revealed that the following indicators got the lowest means: achievement press for organizational climate; coping with change for self-efficacy; external regulation for work tasks motivation, and ability to design the teaching activity for pedagogical competence. Hence, school administrators in the Department of Education may focus establishing an academic community where all mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers are oriented towards achieving goals and setting of high academic performance among learners. Trainings may focus on improving teachers' ability to adopt new instructional methods as mandated by the new curriculum changes. In-service trainings may also include motivation aspects focusing on the accountability of teachers in doing their job as MTB teachers. With this, teachers as being exposed to various trainings can improve their ability to design learning activities appropriate for diverse mother tongue learners.

Further, it was found that organizational climate, self-efficacy, and work tasks motivation have significant relationship with the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers. Therefore, school administrators who are actively engaged in school planning and teacher development initiatives, may consider these results in strengthening organizational climate that encourages self-efficacy of teachers along with the maintenance of teachers' work motivation in schools to improve pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers.

Since the best fitting model for the pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers was best anchored on self-efficacy and work tasks motivation, it is recommended that schools may enhance their teacher professional development programs. For instance, they may consider training programs focusing on the development of teachers' ability in mother tongue-based multilingual education instruction. Though there were previous trainings conducted already, it is imperative for the Department of Education to retool teachers.

The findings of this study may be used as a guide for harnessing pedagogical competence of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers and implementing a more appropriate pedagogical training model in local contexts.

Similar study may be conducted using a mixed-methods approach involving qualitative data collection from the lens of the mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers.

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